

The Effects of Electrodeless Discharge on Potassium Chlorate, Bromate and Iodate.

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In a previous paper Bhatnagar, Sharma, and Mitra (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1928, 5, 379) have shown that under the influence of electrodeless discharge naphthalene is converted into a compound whose composition is represented by the empirical formula $C_{24}H_{20}O$. J. J. Thomson (*Proc. Phys. Soc., Lond.*, 1928, 40, 79) has further shown that the gas through which the electrodeless discharge passes enters into chemical combination and produces compounds some of which are quite unexpected. The discharge evidently puts some of the atoms and molecules into an excited state which enhances their chemical activity. Thus he found that magnesium oxide under the influence of the discharge combines with oxygen to form a higher oxide. Similar results were obtained with calcium oxide and zinc oxide.

The present communication deals with the effects of the electrodeless discharge on potassium chlorate, bromate and iodate. These substances have been found by the author to emit a beautiful blue fluorescence in a Tesla tube. Incidentally the behaviour of molecules when excited by such agents as heat and ultra-violet light has been compared with what happens under the Tesla discharge.

EXPERIMENTAL.

The apparatus for obtaining the electrodeless discharge was the same as described by Bhatnagar, Shrivastava, Mathur, and Sharma (*Phil. Mag.*, 1928, p. 1227) with the modification that the X-ray dental transformer was replaced by a Siemens transformer having a ratio of 200 primary to 45,000 secondary.

The substance to be exposed was put in the discharge tube and a glass plate was cemented on to one end of the tube by Everette's vacuum wax. The other end of the tube was drawn out and connected to a manometer through a wash-bottle containing liquid paraffin. The manometer was connected to a Cenco Hyvac pump *via* another wash-bottle which also contained liquid paraffin. All

joints were made air-tight with Everette's wax and the tube was exhausted to a pressure of 1—3 mm. of mercury when the discharge was allowed to pass for 7 hours generally. The glow obtained varied in colour in the case of chlorate from violet to sky blue, light to dark violet and sometimes sky blue in the case of bromate and bright violet in the case of iodate. The substance in the tube was shaken from time to time to expose a fresh surface to the discharge. After exposure the substance was taken out of the discharge tube by removing the glass plate. All the work was carried out at the room temperature.

Tests and Estimations.

Chlorate.—When taken out of the tube, the exposed sample of the chlorate exhibited a blue opalescence which disappeared in the course of 24—48 hours. The sample also smelt distinctly of chlorine and gave tests showing the presence of chloride and hypochlorite. A sample of the original chlorate was tested for these radicles but gave negative results. No chlorite and perchlorate could be detected in the exposed sample. The following types of results were obtained with 100 gm. of exposed potassium chlorate.

	Expt. 1.	Expt. 2.	Expt. 3.
Hypochlorite . . .	0'001636 g.	0'001680 g.	0'005303 g.
Chloride . . .	0'1569	0'1600	0'16525

Bromate.—When taken out of the discharge tube the bromate gave a smell of bromine and showed tests corresponding to the production of a hypobromite and bromide. No free bromine could be detected. The original sample of bromate did not give any tests for hypobromite and bromide. The following results were obtained with 100 g. of exposed potassium bromate.

	Expt. 1.	Expt. 2.	Expt. 3.
Hypobromite . . .	0'001388 g.	0'001491 g.	0'002111 g.
Bromide . . .	0'08364	0'09770	0'05097

Iodate.—The iodate when removed from the tube had acquired a brownish colour and smelt and gave tests showing the presence of free iodine. No iodide could be detected. 100 Gm. of exposed iodate gave 0'02199, 0'02205, and 0'01610 g. of iodine in three different experiments.

with certain substances reduction can also take place. The products obtained are not those which are obtained when these substances are heated or when they are exposed to the ultra-violet radiations as the following table shows :—

Exciting agent.	Potassium chlorate.	Potassium bromate.	Potassium iodate.
Heat.	KCl + Oxygen via KClO ₄ with traces of Cl. ¹	KBr + Oxygen with traces of bromine. ²	KI + Oxygen with traces of iodine, no per- or other oxy-salts at any stage of decom- position. ³
Ultra-violet radiation.	Oxygen + KCl ⁴	Oxygen + KBr ⁴	Oxygen + KI + I ⁴
Electrodeless discharge.	KCl + KClO	KBr + KBrO	Iodine.

From the above it will be clear that no hypo-salts have been detected as a result of the decomposition of the chlorate, bromate and iodate either by heat or ultra-violet radiations. In the case of chlorates, the perchlorate is formed but the per-salts have not been detected in the case of the iodates.

In these experiments the presence of per-salts has not been detected. Hypochlorite and hypobromite have been detected. Ordinarily these salts are not produced by decomposition of the chlorate and bromate; in fact they are oxidised to the chlorate and bromate. In the case of iodates, iodine has been found to be present and the presence of iodides has not been detected. The invidious results in the case of iodates may be explained by assuming that $KIO_3 \rightarrow KI + KIO$ and that KI and KIO further react to form I and K₂O. The reaction $KI + KIO + H_2O \rightarrow I + KOH$ has been studied by Schonbein (*J. pr. Chem.*, 1861, *i*, 84, 385), and Taylor (*Chem. News*, 1897, 76, 27; *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1900, 77, 725), who have shown it to be a reversible one. Evidence of the presence of potassium hypoiodite was found in the decomposition of potassium iodate at a pressure of

¹ Billiet and Crafts (*Brit Assoc. Rep.*, 1882, p. 493); Teeds (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1887, 81, 283); Frankland and Dugliwall (*ibid*, p. 274); Schonbein (*J. pr. Chem.*, 1855, *i*, 63, 96); Leeds (*Chem. News*, 1880, 42, 304); Cook (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1894, 65, 802).

² Stas (*Mem. Acad. Belgique*, 1865, 36, 116); Cook (*loc. cit.*).

³ Rammelsburg (*Pogg. Ann.*, 1869, 137, 307; 1839, 44, 577); Cook (*loc. cit.*).

⁴ Oertel (*Biochem. Z.*, 1914, 60, 480; *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1914, 106, 321); Suryanarayana (*J. Sci. Assoc. of Maharaja's College, Vizianagram*, 1924, 2, 12; *Chem. Abs.*, 1924, 18, 3548); Mathews and Curtis (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1914, 18, 641).

13—15 mm. Attempts were made to test the complete validity of this view by testing the residue left after extraction of the free iodine with carbon disulphide but it was found that it gave a neutral reaction to litmus.

The results outlined above show that the effect of the electrodeless discharge on potassium chlorate, bromate, and iodate is not analogous to the effect of heat or ultra-violet radiations.

A theoretical explanation of these results will be given in a subsequent paper.

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